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Project Acronym: MONPLAS

Project title: Monitoring Micro- and Nanoplastics

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Multispectral imaging flow cytometry for assessment of microplastic particles

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History of edits:		
Version	Date	Amendments:
v1.0	20.05.2021	Initial DMP draft based on DMPonline
vN+1		<i>e.g. Treat all RESEARCH OUTPUTS as FAIR & open “data”</i>
vN+2		<i>e.g. Explore converting DMP to machine actionable DMP</i>

AMBITION FOR DATA MANGEMENT

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is a living document und will be adjusted, extended and maintained alongside with the progress of my research project. The ambition for this DMP aims towards transparent, reproducible and reusable research outputs. Despite traditional research outputs like scientific publications and conference contributions, this DMP also manages progress outputs that document my journey as a PhD student. This document underlines the aim of OpenAccess data and builds the basis for dialogue, between me as a researcher, my host institution the Leibniz Institute of Photonic Technology in synergy with MONPLAS Disclosure protocols, Intellectual Property Right (IPR) exploitation, in collaboration with the MONPLAS Exploitation Management Committee and the Dissemination Committee and of course, this community, which the data outputs of my project are intended to serve.

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INITIAL HORIZON 2020 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN FOR MONPLAS – ESR 9

ADMIN DETAILS

Project Name: Multispectral imaging flow cytometry for assessment of microplastic particles

Project Identifier: MONPLAS-ESR-9

Principal Investigator / Researcher: Julia Sophie Boeke

Affiliation: Leibniz-Institute of Photonic Technology (Leibniz-IPHT)

Project Data Contact: Library of Leibniz-IPHT, +49 (0)3641 206-00, bibliothek@leibniz-ipht.de

Description: Development and application of multispectral imaging flow cytometry for assessment of microplastic particles. The project aims to develop and apply multispectral imaging flow cytometry (mIFC) to assess microplastic particles in a size range between 2 and 40 µm based on their geometrical and colorimetric properties. The measurement is performed utilizing mIFC as a high-throughput method. Therefore, a custom mIFC system equipped with a multispectral imaging detector will be developed and utilized within the PhD study. Different plastic materials exhibit different affinities to dye molecules (lipophilic, hydrophilic, cationic, anionic dyes). This will be used to discriminate microplastic materials based on the chemometric analysis of the incorporated dye molecules. The number and size of microplastic particles will be detected as well to determine their content. Combined with appropriate separation and enrichment methods, mIFC can assess microplastics from various matrices such as seawater, sediments, food, drinks, plants and tissues.

Funder: European Commission (Horizon 2020)

DATA MANAGEMENT SUMMARY

Research at Leibniz-IPHT conforms with the given Guidelines for 'Safeguarding Good Research Practice. Code of Conduct', published by the German Research Foundation (dt. Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)) in 2019 [1].

These Guidelines are implemented at the Leibniz-IPHT and form the framework of the Data Management Plan for the MONPLAS/ESR9 project. Specific implementations of these guidelines for the Leibniz-IPHT are published in the following documents:

- Leibniz-IPHT: Rules for safeguarding good scientific practice (2019) [2]
- Leibniz-IPHT: Code of Conduct at the Leibniz Institute of Photonic Technology (2019) [3]
- Leibniz Association: Guidelines for Good Scientific Practice in the Leibniz Association (2019) [4]

1. Data summary

Data and information are generated during scientific experiments and subsequent data analysis. Experiments are performed to confirm or reject the scientific hypothesis for the assessment of microplastic materials. Digital data is generated in standard data file formats. Reports are generated as text files or derived formats. For each version, a .pdf print-out is created and stored within the data repository. Figures and plots are created in standard file formats or .pdf. Derived result tables are generated as .csv-files or derived formats.

Recipes for data processing are either provided as reports, executable scripts or task-related data analysis application. Reports on the utilized experimental infrastructure are part of the 'Material and Methods' section of a respective publication. Existing data is re-used. Data is generated by the respective operators of the experiment using the particular experimental infrastructure. The expected storage data size ranges between 10 kb and 100 GB per conducted experiment. In the context of scientific experiments, the data will be useful to fellow researchers. The results on the measurement of microplastics will be helpful to the public.

The following table shows expected data outputs:

Type	Volume	Storage/Dissemination	Expiration	Format
Research diary	MB, physical book	Laptop, Hard disk, Laboratory PC, Leibniz-IPHT's data center, stored by the Research Group	up to 10 years	.txt physical book
Physical samples	ml	Laboratory facilities (fridge, freezers, chemical storage, Eppendorf vessels)	Less than 3 years	-
Literature references	MB	Hard disk, OneDrive cloud, Citavi, Endnote	N/A	.pdf
Pictures (of samples, devices, ...)	MB	Hard disk, OneDrive cloud	3 – 5 years [5]	.jpeg
Raw image data	GB	Laptop, Hard disk, Laboratory PC, Leibniz-IPHT's data center	up to 10 years	.jpeg .tiff
Raw spectral data	GB	Laptop, Hard disk, Laboratory PC, Leibniz-IPHT's data center	up to 10 years	.ptir .bsp .csv .spc
Processed spectral data	GB	Laptop, Hard disk, Laboratory PC, Leibniz-IPHT's data center	up to 10 years	.csv .spc
MONPLAS deliverables	MB	Laptop, Hard disk, MONPLAS Box cloud server	N/A	.pptx .pdf
PhD status reports	MB	BatchCard of Leibniz-IPHT, MONPLAS Box cloud server	N/A	.pptx .pdf
PhD status presentations	MB	BatchCard of Leibniz-IPHT, MONPLAS Box cloud server	N/A	.pptx
Scientific presentations	MB	Laptop, Hard disk, Laboratory PC, Leibniz-IPHT's data center	N/A	.pptx .pdf
Standard Operation Procedures	MB	Laptop, Hard disk, Laboratory PC, Leibniz-IPHT's data center	up to 10 years	.pdf
Research papers, alongside with documentation and necessary raw data	MB-GB	Hard disk, Leibniz-IPHT library, Journals data repository, LinkedIn (optionally), Friedrich-Schiller University library	up to 10 years	.pdf .txt

Table 1: Summary of expected data outputs by type and assigned storage volume, location, expiration and formats.

2. FAIR data

2. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Experimental data and research results are stored utilizing the infrastructure provided by the Leibniz-IPHT. The implementation conforms with the rules as mentioned above and guidelines of the DFG [1].

Further experimental data may be deposited as digital supplementary information to published scientific papers. Standards for data deposition, indexing and denomination will conform with the given rules of the publisher/ data hosting organization.

The naming convention used for the root folder is standardized as YYYYMMDD_NameOfTheExperiment, including specific identifiers (e.g. method and sample). A readme.txt contains information of the version and key information on the experiment, including names and organization of all operators and contributors, together with the key settings and parameters for the root folder of the data repository. Typically, the readme.txt is created at the start of the experiment and used as a notebook by the operator. Software versioning also follows the approach to be identified by YYYY-MM-DD, associated modules are stored in a .zip folder before extensive revisioning. The name of the experiment can be used as a keyword for storage-wide search. The display of the date in the root folder name allows clear versioning. If necessary an additional version number is used. Metadata is created as key-value tuples and stored in .xml- or text files.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Experimental data may be deposited as digital supplementary information alongside the published scientific papers. The deposited data repository will be complete and includes raw data and recipes, outlining the data processing workflow. The reported findings and results can be reproduced independently from the deposited data and described rules. Standards for data deposition, indexing and denomination will conform to the given rules of the publisher, data host organization and provider.

Specific methods and software tools to access the data will be documented and described in the scientific publications alongside recipes for the data processing. The supplementary information will be published as OpenAccess.

2.3. Making data interoperable

For common and reoccurring tasks, task-specific data acquisition and processing apps will be created and utilized. The structure of the generated data is part of the documentation of the app. The apps will be created utilizing a component-based software toolkit (name: Leibniz-IPHT Microfluidic Workbench (Mwb) Toolkit), capable of aggregating multiple reusable software components for data acquisition and data analysis into a single app with a graphical user interface. Management of project-related settings is a mandatory part of the app. Each component can save and reloading its respective settings from key-value lists stored in .txt (or .xml) format.

Figure 1 shows an example of the FluidManagementApp for the control of microfluidic experiments.

Figure 1: MwbToolkit App for pressure-based control of microfluidic experiments. Left: Project settings tab. Right: Tab with settings dialogue for controlling the pressure settings for the experiment. The app controls the Fluidgent MFCS System (FluidgentFrance)

The use of standard methodology and vocabulary, as well as the app together with documentation, ensures inter-disciplinary interoperability. Meta data management is always included, for each generated data item.

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

According to the contract, all produced results become the property of the Leibniz-IPHT. Licensing models must be defined and confirmed by the Leibniz-IPHT. The provided data will be stored for ten years by the Leibniz-IPHT.

3. Allocation of resources

We aim for OpenAccess publications. Costs will be covered through the MONPLAS funds, Leibniz-IPHT, and publication funds of the Leibniz association.

Responsible for the data management of this project is Julia Sophie Boeke. The Leibniz-IPHT covers costs and provides the infrastructure for long-term preservation.

4. Data security

The Leibniz-IPHT maintains data storage for ten years. Optionally, large data sets related to published results can be deposited on open data storage services for long-term data storage and accessibility.

5. Ethical aspects

It is covered in the former sections.

6. Other issues and references

The following national and departmental procedures for data management are applicable:

- DFG Guidelines:
 - [1] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (2019): Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice. Code of Conduct. Available online at <https://zenodo.org/record/3923602#.YHks4j9CRPZ>.
- Leibniz-IPHT Guidelines:
 - [2] Leibniz Institute of Photonic Technology (2019): Rules for safeguarding good scientific practice. Available online at <https://intranet.leibniz-ipht.de/en/guidelines.html>.
 - [3] Leibniz Institute of Photonic Technology (2019): Code of Conduct at the Leibniz Institute of Photonic Technology. Available online at <https://intranet.leibniz-ipht.de/en/guidelines.html>.
- Leibniz Guidelines:
 - [4] Leibniz Association: Guidelines for Good Scientific Practice in the Leibniz Association (2019), Available online at https://www.leibniz-gemeinschaft.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Bilder_und_Downloads/%C3%9Cber_uns/Integrit%C3%A4t/Guidelines_for_Good_Scientific_Practice_in_the_Leibniz_Association.pdf
- Additional references:
 - [5] Storage Craft 'Data storage lifespans: How long will media really last?': <https://blog.storagecraft.com/data-storage-lifespan/> (Accessed 18.05.2021)